

Identification of Export-Oriented Sectors in the Region of Zacatecas after Covid-19

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to identify the sectors with export potential in the region prior to the health crisis and their vulnerability to it. Following the theory of urban economic base, the export capacity of Zacatecas' sectors is examined using location quotients. It is found that the nature of each sector's production process and the management of the pandemic itself favoured an increase in export potential for some activities, while in other cases, the effect was the opposite. The productive structure of the region is characterized as traditional and non-specialized. Finally, it is suggested to leverage the export potential maintained by certain sectors to contribute to regional economic growth.

KEYWORDS: sectors, export, region, COVID-19, economic growth

JEL code: R10, O14, O54

INTRODUCTION

Following the health crisis caused by COVID-19, which was accompanied by the cessation or restriction of most productive activities, the various states in Mexico have faced the economic aftermath during the now-called post-pandemic period (Jiménez-Bandala et al., 2021). The overall situation in the state of Zacatecas already presented issues related to low levels of industrialization and innovation, coupled with high levels of poverty and inequality. Among primary activities, mining holds the greatest weight, but it is predominantly carried out by foreign companies that often do not contribute to the domestic market. On the other hand, agriculture has been losing its relative importance, and there are signs of substitutive tertiary (Gaytán, Jiménez & Pérez, 2018).

This pre-existing situation was further exacerbated by the health crisis, impacting various hierarchies and sectoral imbalances, ultimately affecting the state's economic growth and development. From a regional perspective, Zacatecas lacks functional interrelation among economic sectors and a consolidated internal market with beneficial intersectoral productive linkages (Gaytán Alfaro, 2016). Within the field of economic science, regional and sectoral analysis perspectives provide tools to diagnose this situation and offer potential pathways to recovery in the face of such issues.

As Capello (2006) mentions, regional economics focuses on explaining regional growth and development, encompassing the study of endogenous determinants of growth. For instance, as explained by Asuad Sanén (2006), the theory of the urban economic base posits that a region's exports drive greater economic growth since export activity requires backward linkages to support local economy services and forward linkages to expand the residential sector.

With these postulates in mind, the objective of this research is to identify the productive sectors of Zacatecas as triggers for regional development before and after the health crisis based on their export capacity.

Body text

The Location Quotient coefficients (LQ_i), formulated by Blair (1991), compare the relative importance or percentage participation of an industry sector in a regional economy to that of the national economy. This allows for the analysis of the export characteristics of different economic sectors in a region.

These coefficients are calculated by weighting the value-added or employment in a sector of economic activity for a region against the corresponding value in the comparison zone, which, in this case, is the national economy. For this research, the value-added will be used due to its direct relationship with economic growth. Data relating to this variable will be obtained from the National Institute of

“Identification of Export-Oriented Sectors in the Region of Zacatecas after Covid-19”

Statistics and Geography [INEGI] (2023) for the years 2019 and 2021. See Equation 1:

$$LQ_i = \left(\frac{e_i}{e_t}\right) / \left(\frac{E_i}{E_t}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where e_i represents the regional value-added for each industry sector, e_t represents the total regional value-added, E_i represents the national value-added for each industry sector and E_t represents the total national value-added.

The value obtained for this indicator is interpreted based on its equality, inferiority, or superiority to one: When

the LQ coefficient is greater than one, the regional participation of that sector is higher than the national average, indicating an export capacity. When the LQ coefficient is less than one, there is a limited representation of that activity in the region. When the LQ coefficient is equal to one, the presence of that sector is equivalent to the national average.

These interpretations are summarized in Table 1. The analysis of LQ coefficients will provide valuable insights into the export potential of different economic sectors in the region of Zacatecas before and after the COVID-19 crisis.

Table 1: Interpretation of location coefficients.

LQi Values	Interpretation
LQi = 1	The region produces in the same proportion as the national average.
LQi < 1	The region does not have export potential in the sector.
LQi > 1	The region has export potential in the sector.

Source: Own elaboration (Self-made).

Next, the change between the two proposed years is compared through the location coefficients in the region.

Location Quotient (LQ) coefficients in Zacatecas. The calculations obtained for the LQ coefficients in this region are presented in Table 2.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the results is to compare the changes between the two proposed years (2019 and 2021) using the

Table 2: Location coefficients for Zacatecas 2019 and 2021

SECTOR	2019			2021		
	Código	VAB R (ei)	VAB N (Ei)	LQi	VAB R (ei)	VAB N (Ei)
11	12,637	592,490	2.48	15,286	611,867	2.82
21	15,116	856,107	2.05	16,056	856,651	2.12
22	1,388	285,956	0.56	1,202	221,816	0.61
23	13,268	1,223,983	1.26	12,593	1,092,811	1.30
31-33	18,574	2,938,819	0.74	18,023	2,896,827	0.70
43	12,650	1,561,600	0.94	11,863	1,552,550	0.86
46	14,862	1,659,762	1.04	14,938	1,679,716	1.01
48-49	4,606	1,200,337	0.45	4,172	1,099,351	0.43
51	2,059	576,012	0.42	2,063	601,355	0.39
52	4,651	900,616	0.60	4,344	847,803	0.58
53	20,518	2,064,026	1.16	20,690	2,103,918	1.11
54	1,119	398,486	0.33	1,265	359,231	0.40
55	3	77,396	0.00	3	128,725	0.00
56	1,534	412,193	0.43	1,179	502,846	0.26
61	9,873	367,830	3.12	9,411	674,144	1.58
62	4,001	709,971	0.66	3,915	410,437	1.08
71	261	348,517	0.09	192	56,604	0.38
72	2,468	108,525	2.64	1,757	317,805	0.62
81	2,526	695,564	0.42	2,459	323,594	0.86
93	9,769	687,870	1.65	9,372	702,644	1.51
Totales (et y Et)	151,882	17,666,059	-	150,782	17,040,694	-

Source: Own elaboration based on data from INEGI.

As observed, the region of Zacatecas had eight sectors with export capacity (values shaded in gray) in the period before the pandemic. These sectors are 11 (agriculture, livestock

raising, forestry, fishing, and hunting), 21 (mining), 23 (construction), 46 (retail trade), 53 (real estate and rental services of movable and intangible goods), 61 (educational

services), 72 (accommodation and food service activities), and 93 (legislative, governmental, justice, and international and extraterritorial organizations activities).

It is noteworthy that the highest LQ coefficient values are related to primary activities, such as sector 11, secondary activities, like sector 21, or non-specialized tertiary activities, such as sectors 61 and 72. This pre-pandemic export characterization reflects the region's productive orientation towards traditional sectors. This, in turn, contributes to the overall low value aggregation, as described in the work of Gaytán Alfaro (2020), which delves into the repercussions of the lack of consolidation of the regional internal market.

During the pandemic, there were changes in the existence of export potential for some sectors. Sector 62 (health and social assistance services) managed to reach export capacity, while sector 72 (accommodation and food service activities) lost its export capacity.

The increase in export potential in sector 62 can be attributed to the demand created by the health emergency, reflecting that the regional economic response to the crisis was greater compared to the national average. This result is supported by various studies, like that of Salas et al. (2020), which examine the implications of different regional pandemic management approaches in comparison to the national context.

On the other hand, the loss of export potential in sector 72 reflects the shock caused by the lockdown resulting from the pandemic for sectors directly involving interstate mobility of people. Sector 72 has been extensively analysed, considering it as one of the sectors most affected by the crisis. Studies such as Enríquez et al. (2021), González Damián (2020), and Ríos Elorza (2020) analyse the regional and structural implications of the decline in tourism. In the context of this study, the loss of export potential reveals that Zacatecas was unable to maintain its tourist orientation compared to the national average, indicating a lack of consolidation in this activity in the region.

Sectors 11, 21, and 23 showed an increase in their export potential, indicating that despite the pandemic restrictions, these activities, having been previously consolidated, managed to increase their regional economic importance. The problem lies in the fact that these sectors are traditional, which prolongs the region's stay in an unmodernized economy focused on extractive-industrial activities. Such a development path cannot ensure sustained long-term economic growth, missing the opportunity for reorienting the region's development trajectory, as mentioned by Zamora et al. (2020).

Conversely, sectors 46, 53, 61, and 93 experienced a decrease in their export potential in the region, although they still retained some regional export capacity. In the case of sector 46, this represents a loss of relevance for retail trade at the regional level, which can be explained by the asymmetric measures implemented during the lockdown that particularly

affected small commercial enterprises of this type. As explained by Béjar Tinoco et al. (2022), despite the relief provided by the electronic commerce dynamics for businesses, it was mostly the larger companies that took advantage of this palliative measure, while retail trade could not benefit from it to the same extent. Consequently, this further demonstrates the lack of technological development in economic activities in Zacatecas.

A similar case to sector 72 is sector 53, related to real estate and rental services of movable and intangible goods, which were linked to people's mobility. This also reflects the lack of consolidation of this sector in the region, as observed in the work of Hernández (2022).

Finally, sectors 61 and 93 also lost relevance in comparison to national production, witnessing a decrease in their export potential. In Zacatecas, 94% of educational activities are public (Secretary of Public Education, 2022). Considering the composition of this sector and the nature of sector 93, the loss of export potential in public realms indicates less favourable regional government management compared to the national equivalent, and the differential explains this decline. This is because during the pandemic, public activities were not carried out with the same efficiency as at the national level, which is crucial given the significant role of state management in economic development in Zacatecas (Chávez Ruiz, 2019). This also demonstrates a lack of technological advancement in the sector, as these activities are conducive to digital or distance learning methods.

CONCLUSIONS

In the economic context of deeper structural problems, the pandemic situation, as a conjunctural issue, highlights change in the productive fabric of the Zacatecas region. Initially, this study hypothesized that activities with export potential before the pandemic would maintain their export capacity during the crisis. However, it was discovered that the effects were differentiated due to the nature of each production process and the state-imposed measures of economic shutdown.

While health services activities increased their export capacity, tourism-related activities experienced the opposite trend. This outcome resulted from the very nature of the pandemic and the subsequent lockdown measures. However, primarily extractive activities and services with low value-added, both foundational elements of the Zacatecas economy, remained relatively unaffected and even increased their export potential.

Therefore, in the process of reorganizing economic activities, it is essential to emphasize reorienting the export potential towards sectors that were less favoured during the health crisis. It is also suggested to capitalize on the regional development potential represented by activities that managed to improve their export potential despite the crisis, especially in a growth path that seeks a transition to activities with higher value-added. Gradually improving the state's

economic situation, not only in the post-pandemic period but also in the long term.

Overall, understanding the dynamics of export potential in different sectors during and after the pandemic provides valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to chart a path towards a more resilient and diversified regional economy. By capitalizing on the strengths and mitigating the weaknesses identified in this research, Zacatecas can better navigate future challenges and foster sustainable economic growth in the post-pandemic era.

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